

***In-vitro* Studies on Taigor (Dimethoate 30% EC) on leguminous plants**

Sonawane TP

Assistant professor, Department of Botany, Jijamata College of Science and Arts Dyaneshwarnagar Bhende. Tal. Newasa, Dist. Ahilyanagar, Maharashtra.414605
Affiliated by Savitribai Phule Pune University, Pune, MS, India
Email: tejalsonawane627@gmail.com

Manuscript details:

Received: 09.04.2026
Accepted: 18.05.2026
Published:30.05.2026

Cite this article as:

Sonawane TP (2026) *In-vitro* Studies on Taigor (Dimethoate 30% EC) on leguminous plants, *Int. J. of Life Sciences*, 14 (1A):247-251.
<https://doi.org/10.5281/zenodo.20685455>

Available online on <http://www.ijlsci.in>
ISSN: 2320-964X (Online)
ISSN: 2320-7817 (Print)

Open Access This article is licensed under a Creative Commons Attribution 4.0 International License, which permits use, sharing, adaptation, distribution and reproduction in any medium or format, as long as you give appropriate credit to the original author(s) and the source, provide a link to the Creative Commons licence, and indicate if changes were made. The images or other third-party material in this article are included in the article's Creative Commons licence, unless indicated otherwise in a credit line to the material. If material is not included in the article's Creative Commons licence and your intended use is not permitted by statutory regulation or exceeds the permitted use, you will need to obtain permission directly from the copyright holder. To view a copy of this licence, visit <http://creativecommons.org/licenses/by/4.0/>.

ABSTRACT

The present investigation carried out at Botany department Jijamata College Bhende. To study the effect of taigor on seed germination and photosynthetic pigment of *Vigna radiata L.* and *Vigna aconitifolia L.* During the study various concentrations (control,0.1%,0.2%,0.3%,0.4% & 0.5%) were applied to study the effect of taigor on the seed germination and seedling growth of leguminous plant. It was recorded that the decrease in seed germination and photosynthetic pigment at higher concentration where is increase in above parameters at lower concentration i.e. the taigor is concentration co-related. Dimethoate a widely used insecticide affects photosynthetic pigment and growth rate. This impact can be attributed to the inhibition of chlorophyll biosynthesis and disruption of lipid membrane. This finding suggested that taigor can be toxic to leguminous plant. The result contributed to understanding potential non- target effect of organophosphate formulations on crop species and highlight the value in vitro assays in preliminary phytotoxicity screening.

Keywords: Insecticide, Taigor, Leguminous plant

INTRODUCTION

Taigor is a commercial formulation of dimethoate, an organophosphate insecticide widely used in agriculture to control a broad range of insect pests. Dimethoate (O, O dimethyl S- methylcarbamoymethyl phosphorodithiote) acts as a systemic and contact insecticide meaning it can be absorbed by plant tissue and also kill insect upon direct exposure. It is commonly applied to crops such as legumes and field crops to manage pests like aphids, whiteflies and mites. Leguminous plants belong to the family fabaceae (Leguminosae) one of the largest families of flowering plants (Kabir et al) Leguminous plants are known for their unique ability to form a symbiotic relationship with rhizobium bacteria in their root nodules. Legumes play an important role in sustainable agriculture and crop rotation system. Due to their economic and ecological significance leguminous plants are often used in scientific studies related to seed germination, plant growth, soil improvement and the effect of various chemical treatment. Mung bean (*Vigna radiata L.*) is an important leguminous crop belonging to the family

fabaceae. It is commonly known as green gram. It is a short duration crop and is valued for its high nutritional content and soil enriching properties which helps in atmospheric nitrogen fixation (Justin G and e.tal) This improves soil fertility. Due to its fast germination and uniform growth and sensitivity to environmental changes, *Vigna radiata* is frequently used as a model plant in laboratory experiment to study seed germination, seedling growth, phytotoxicity, stress physiology, agrochemicals. *Vigna aconitifolia* (jacq.) murehal commonly known as moth bean is an important drought tolerant leguminous crop belonging to the family fabaceae. moth bean is an important drought -tolerant leguminous crop belonging to the family fabaceae. moth bean is valued for its nutritional importance as its seeds are rich in protein, carbohydrate, vitamin and essential minerals (Kundoo.A and e.tal) Due its adaptability to harsh environmental conditions. *Vigna aconitifolia* is frequently used in research studies related to drought tolerance, seed germination, stress physiology, soil improvement and agrochemical impact assessment.

Objective

To Evaluate the effect of Tafgor (Dimethoate 30% EC) on seed germination and early seedling growth of selected leguminous plants under in vitro condition. To study the effect of different concentration of Tafgor (Dimethoate 30%Ec) on the germination percentage leguminous seeds. To assess the impact of Tafgor on root length and shoot length of seedling.

MATERIAL AND METHODS

1.Collection of seed sample – The seed of mung bean, moth bean was selected for the present study. The seeds are collected then soaked in water for 3 hours and brought to the laboratory for further procedure. Local varieties of mung bean, moth bean seeds are used with uniform size, color, and weight were choose for experimental purpose.

2.Different concentration of insecticide tafgor:

Different concentration of insecticide tafgor was prepared i.e. control, 0.1%, 0.2%, 0.3%, 0.4% and 0.5% then the seeds of mung bean, moth bean was soaked in that concentrated solution for 3 hours. 0.1% concentrated solution means 0.1 ml tafgor added to a 99.9 ml water.

0.2% concentrated solution = 0.2ml tafgor + 99.8ml water

0.3% concentrated solution = 0.3ml of tafgor + 99.7ml water

0.4% concentrated solution = 0.4 ml of tafgor + 99.6ml water

0.5% concentrated solution = 0.5 ml of tafgor + 99.5 ml water

And 100 ml water called control. After that all seeds are sowed on tray in cocopeat in laboratory. Because cocopeat is a sterile medium, free from harmful pathogens weed seeds, and pests commonly found in traditional soil. This sterility minimizes the risks of plant diseases and reduces the need for chemical pesticide and herbicides, fostering a healthier and more organic growing environment. Then watered the seeds daily.

Observation parameter –

1.Determination of root length and shoot length

Root length – The length of the main roots structure that grows downwards in to the soil.

Shoot length – Measurement – Root length and shoot length are typically measured in centimeters (m)

Purpose – This measurement is important for assessing seed germination, seedling development and overall health of the plant.

2. Chlorophyll estimation – Chlorophyll estimation involves determining the amount of chlorophyll pigments. Primarily chlorophyll a and chlorophyll b present in a sample, such as plant leaf.

Procedure:

Weight about 0.5 gm of fresh tissue. Cut the leaves into small pieces. Grind the leaf pieces in a mortar and pestle with 10 ml of acetone until the tissue is fully homogenized. Centrifuged the extract at 3000 rpm for 10 minutes to remove debris. Transfer the clear supernatant to a clean cuvette. Measure the absorbance at 645 nm and 663 nm a UV- visible Spectrophotometer. chlorophyll content is a key indicator of photosynthetic efficiency and overall plant health. This study investigated the effects of varying concentration of mung bean, moth bean. On the chlorophyll of mung bean seedling. Seed were pretreated with concentration of control 2%, 4% ,6%, 8%. after a specific growth period the chlorophyll a chlorophyll b content estimated using standard spectrophotometric method chlorophyll a and b content decreases progressively with 8%.

3. Determination of root length and shoot length:

Final measurement of shoot and root length was taken after 21 days of growth of test species. Shoot and root length of all plants were measured in centimeters (cm) using ruler.

4. Chlorophyll estimation: A sample preparation a known of plant tissue Ex. 5 gm is ground and extracted with a solvent like 80% acetone. chlorophyll estimation involves determining the amount of chlorophyll pigment, primarily chlorophyll a and b, in plant tissue or other samples. This is typically done using spectrophotometry or fluorometry after extracting the pigments from the sample using an appropriate solvent.

RESULTS

Reduced growth rates: insecticide, particularly organophosphate compounds like dimethoate, can reduce growth rates in leguminous plants.

Inhibited chlorophyll biosynthesis: dimethoate has been shown to inhibit chlorophyll biosynthesis which is essential for photosynthesis.

Impact on lipid membranes: Organophosphates insecticide can affect the fluidity of lipid membrane, potentially disturbing cellular functions.

Table 1:Shoot length and Root length of *Vigna radiata*

Concentration of TAFGOR	Shoot length	Root Length	Total Shoot length & Root Length
Control	17.6	3.5	21.1
0.1 %	12.2	2.7	14.9
0.2 %	12.3	3.1	15.4
0.3 %	11.8	2.0	13.8
0.4 %	10.5	2.8	13.3
0.5 %	9.0	2.4	11.4

Graph 1: Shoot length and Root length of *Vigna radiata*

Table 2 (Shoot length and Root length of (*Vigna aconitifolia*))

Concentration of TAFGOR	Shoot length	Root Length	Total Shoot length & Root Length
Control	15.8	10.0	25.8
0.1 %	4.5	3.6	8.1
0.2 %	4.2	3.2	7.4
0.3 %	2.5	1.8	4.3
0.4 %	2.2	1.4	3.6
0.5 %	1.7	1.1	2.8

Graph No.2 (Shoot length and Root length of (Vigna aconitifolia))

Table 3 :(Chlorophyll Estimation)

Treatment	Chl.a (mg/g)	Chl.b (mg/g)	Total Chl. (mg/g)
Control	8.70	5.34	14.04
0.1 %	6.76	4.08	10.84
0.2 %	4.98	3.20	8.19
0.3 %	2.50	2.40	4.90
0.4 %	1.25	1.15	2.40
0.5 %	0.50	0.40	0.90

Graph No.3 (Chlorophyll Estimation)

DISCUSSION

The study of insecticide effects of on leguminous plants, such as mung bean, moth bean reveals that this chemical can have phytotoxic effects. Dimethoate, a widely used insecticide, affects photosynthetic pigment and growth rates. This impact can be attributed to the inhibition of chlorophyll biosynthesis and disruption of lipid membranes.

CONCLUSION

Insecticide can have detrimental effects on leguminous plants, impacting growth rates, chlorophyll biosynthesis, and lipid membrane integrity. These effects can ultimately reduce plant productivity and potentially harm the ecosystem. Further research is necessary to understand the mechanisms behind these effects and

develop more targeted, environmentally friendly pest control strategies.

Conflict of interest

The authors declare no competing interests.

Data Availability Statement: Not applicable.

Correspondence and requests for materials should be addressed to **Sonawane TP**

Reprints and permissions information is available at

<https://www.ijlsci.in/reprints>

REFERENCES

- Kabir M.M., Hossain M.A., Farhat T., Yasmin S., Niaz and Farhat, R. (2014) International Journal of Innovative Research and Development, 3, 62-68
- Justin G.L.C., Anandhi P. and Jawahar D. (2015) Journal of Entomology and Zoology Studies, 3, 115-121.
- Kundoo A.A., Showket A., Dar M., Bashir M., Dar M.S., Gul S. and Gulzar (2017) Journal of Entomology and Zoology Studies, 6, 333- 339.

© The Author(s) 2026

Publisher's Note

IJLSCI remains neutral with regard to jurisdictional claims in published maps and institutional affiliations.